

Evaluation of Biodiesel from *Jatropha curcas* Seeds oil using $\text{CoMgFe}_2\text{O}_4$ as Nano-catalysts

Atowon, A. D¹, Ita. E.O²,

¹ Faculty of Engineering, Department of Wood Products Engineering, University of Cross River State, Calabar, Nigeria.

² Faculty of Engineering, Department of Civil Engineering, University of Cross River State, Calabar, Nigeria.

Cite this article: [1]Atowon, A. D and Ita. E.O, "Evaluation of Biodiesel from *Jatropha curcas* Seeds oil using $\text{CoMgFe}_2\text{O}_4$ as Nano-catalysts", International Research Journal of Scientific Studies, vol. August 2024, no. 1, pp. 42–49, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13309406.

Abstract: Biodiesel has been referred to as a basic substitute for diesel fuel because of its numerous promising properties. They are clean, renewable, increase energy security, and environmentally friendly, to meet the widely demand for the running of engine and other equipment powered by fossil fuel. The *Jatropha curcas* seed, oil extraction was characterized using $\text{CoMgFe}_2\text{O}_4$ as Nano-catalysts. Bio-fuel properties, including acid value, pour point, flash point and density, were within the ASTM D6751 limits for biodiesels. The extracted oils were characterized using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). The results of the SEM analysis showed the calcined samples to be a preferred choice due to their large surface area. 55.80% of yield of oil from study showed promising for commercialization of biodiesel production, from *Jatropha curcas*. 84.25 -78.50% biofuel yield was high after four cycle showed reusability of catalyst for continuous reaction for biofuel blend. The result of the properties of the biodiesel and their blend showed their suitability of biodiesel production. Biofuel viscosity placed biofuel in 2D grade (2.0 -4.3mm²/s) and Methyl ester blends of 21:80; these properties are suitable in powering stationary equipment. Inclusion, the seed oil of *jatropha curcas* tran-esterified with $\text{CoMgFe}_2\text{O}_4$ as Nano-catalysts was proven to be a good source for the production of biodiesel.

Keywords: *Jatropha* seed, Catalyst, Tran-esterification and Biofuel.

1. Introduction

Bio-energy is one of the focus of developing countries, in an attempt to eliminate the hazard associated with fossil fuel, as a form of clean energy and sustainability of electricity generation, transportation, agriculture and other industrial activities. Biofuel is an option as clean energy, renewable and environmentally friendly (Kazi et al, 2019, Dash and Lingfa 2018). The world population is increasing rapidly; the demand of clear energy has led to

the use of biodiesel. However, the use of biodiesel is limited and associated with some drawbacks reported that the world crude oil which is the major sources of fossil fuel, reserve shall be exhausted in the next few decades. However, there has been a continuous increase in price of petroleum fuel, shortage in supply and availability, and constant emission of CO₂ from combustion of fuel engine has contributed to global warming (Gholami et al., 2020). This situation has led to

the research for an alternative fuel, which is, not only being environmentally friendly but sustainable, other researcher have reported that, biodiesel is considered as sustainable sources of fuel, clean, non-toxic, biodegradable, renewable and economically viable. Renewable fuel, obtained from vegetable oils or animal fats, low toxicity, in comparison with diesel fuel, degrades more rapidly than diesel fuel, minimizing the environment consequences of biofuel spills. Lower emissions of contaminants; carbon monoxide, particulate matter, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon, aldehydes. Lower health risk, due to reduced emission of carcinogenic substances. No sulfur dioxide (SO₂) emissions. Higher flash point (100°C minimum); Excellent properties as a lubricant (Kara et al., 2019; Ogbu et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2011; Laskar et al., 2018). Feedstock for biofuel production can be sourced from agricultural waste, vegetables, seed oils, waste cooking oil and animal fats. Some are basically cheap feedstocks with higher significant potential for producing sustainable and competitive biofuel due higher percentage of free fatty acid (FFAs) and moisture (Chinomy. et al., 2009; Verma et al., 2016; Pikula et al., 2020). *Jatropha curcas* feedstock for the production of biodiesel has been reported by researchers with specific properties such as low acidity, good oxidation stability and low viscosity. *Jatropha* oil diesel yields easily during conversion process by transesterification requires lower oil catalyst ratio. Other studies show difficulties when converting such stock to biofuel using standard base catalysed trans-esterification method,

moisture and higher FFAs deactive based catalysts, resulting undesired product formation, this resulting on low yield of biofuel (Nayah and Petal, 2010., Ogbu et al 2018). *Jatropha curcas* (Linnaeus) belongs to the family Euphorbiaceae and is closely related to other important cultivated plants like rubber tree and castor etc. Because of its indispensable benefits to mankind it was classified among the first plant in 1753 with a Botanical name “*Jatropha*” from a Greek word *Jatro* “meaning Doctor” and *pha*” meaning nutrition”. The plant is believed to be an origin of South America and Africa but later spread to other continents of the world by the Portuguese settlers. Few phytochemical investigations on its fruits have showed the presence of myricetin and pomolic acid. There have also been claims that it has anti-hyperglycemic properties. In Ghana, the ether extract showed antibiotic activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gubitz et al., 1999. Bengé, 2008, Feitosa et al 2012, White et al 2016). However, several reviews and reports on biofuel production from different feedstock ranging from agricultural waste, vegetable oils, cooking oils animal fat (Verma et al, 2016. Singh et al 2020). Hence, the utilization of vegetable oils as biofuel feedstock has been of great concern as its demands is in competition with the agricultural waste supply in the long term (Ramirez, 2021). The current research focuses on the production of bio-fuel from *Jatropha curcas* seed as feedstock and preliminary evaluation of biofuel property and usability; using nano-catalysts, this will complete the dearth of information gap of utilising another feedstock.

2. Material and methods

2.1 Materials

The reagents were obtained from Ali laboratory Chemical and Reagent, and some of the supporting chemicals were sources from Wood Science lab of Wood Products Engineering, CruTech. The flashpoint was examined and recorded with a Pensky martens flashpoint tester. Soxhlet extractor was used to extract the oil from of *Jatropha curcas* seed as feedstock. The biodiesels burning capacity was evaluated by using TECHNO R175A diesel engine. Calcination was achieved with a Muffle furnace. Digital density meter (model AP PAAR DMA 35) and a viscometer were used to test the seed oil and ester blends densities and the viscosity of the oil.

2.2 Sample collection and oil extraction

The sample of *Jatropha curcas* seeds was source locally from Abi, Cross river, Nigeria. The seed was identified by taxonomist, raw sample as shown in [figure 1](#). Seeds were removed from the fruit cracked and oven dried in control temperature of 70 to 90°C, for five hours. The dried seeds were mill and further sieved via a sieve with a mesh size of 80µm.

2.3 Extraction of oil from *Jatropha Curcas* seed

The oil was obtained by complete extraction using the soxhlet extractor. The dried sample (*Jatropha Curcas* seed) was weighed into the semi-permeable cotton material in the thimble of a Soxhlet extractor. 1200g of the milled seed was placed in three thimbles. 500cm³ of the solvent (n-

hexane) was added into the flake. The set was heated with heating mantle. The process was carried out in 3 to 4 hours, correspondence to the temperature of the solvent used (hexane at 60°C). Solution obtained from the extract was regained through a reflux process for 20 to 30 minutes and then the little moisture content present in the oil was removed through evaporation by increasing the temperature to 70°C for 15 minutes. The oil obtained was weighed and the percentage oil content calculated based on the ratio of extractions of nano-catalyst. Experimental set is shown in [Figure 2](#).

2.4 Trans-esterification process of bio -fuel

(0.5g) of CoMgFe₂O₄ were mixed with (500 mL) and (700mL) of methanol separately to 1000ml of extracted oil of *Jatropha curcas* seed, the mixtures were heated gently at 60 °C below the boiling point of methanol to obtain a methoxide. The catalyst dissolved completely at 180min; the methoxide was poured to flask containing the extracted oil. The mixture was poured to 1000ml of separating funnel and allowed to settle under gravity for 24hour. The pH of biodiesel was determined; Phosphoric acid was added to neutralize the residual catalyst. The separate of bio-diesel from Glycerine; the methoxide solution was mixed in 1000mL containing the treated *Jatropha curcas* seed oil. The mixture was then added to beaker containing methanol of 5:1 and 7:1 ratio then placed in magnetic mechanical stirrer for (3hrs); to obtain a homogenous mixture using a flat plate magnetic stirring. The biodiesel was collected into

a beaker and gently heated with oven under a control temperature of 105°C to eliminate the excess water and allowed to cool to room temperature.

2.5 Bio-diesel Blends Evaluation

Biofuel blends with fossil fuel of 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 100% coded F₂₀, F₄₀, F₆₀, F₈₀ and F₁₀₀ respectively, were prepared to study fuel properties which; included the density, acid value, pour point, viscosity and flash point at various at different temperature.

3. Result and Discussion

The physicochemical properties of the extracted *Jatropha curcas* seed sample are shown in (Table 1). The extracted oil from *Jatropha curcas* was brown and the oil yield percentage was high for large-scale bio-fuel production. The properties of the bio-fuel shows *Jatropha curcas* seed is a good source of oil for biofuel production, the oil shows and conformed to the ASTM standards (Akintayo and Bayer, 2002; Berthiaume and Tremblay, 2006). The free fatty acid of *Jatropha curcas* were from the residual mineral acids from the hydrolysis process of the eaters, and from oxidation by-production in other organic acids. Free fatty acid value is low, this imply that, the extracted oil could be processed into biofuel directly, with the aids of nano-catalyst viz trans-esterification method

The principle saturated fatty acids contained in *Jatropha curcas* were palmitic acid within (5 to 7%); stearic acid (26%), with oleic acid (21%) which exhibited unsaturated behaviours of fatty acid, while linolenic acid with (14%) in composition exhibited a poly

(Thiruvengadaravi et al, 2009). Free fatty acid measures the quality of oil, which depends on the degree of rancidity of unsaturated of fatty acid. The polymerization propensity rises with the degree of unsaturation of the fatty acids. The specific gravity, (Table 1) specific gravity of *Jatropha curcas* oil was observed to be 0.87, the result was consistent with ASTM standard (0.88min) and EN standards (0.86min) (Nayak, and Patel, 2010); this indicate efficiency of biofuel to run diesel engine. The iodine value results showed 110mg/l₂ for the *J. curcas* oil, this imply greater the iodine content, the more unsaturated oil, and faster in polymerises and oxidise, biofuel with higher iodine content showed less stability under higher temperature range. The iodine content is less as Euro norm for iodine value EN 1421 is 120 (Calais and Clark, 2004). The viscosity is 3.8mm²/s at 40°C, the result was consistent with EN standard (5.8max) and ASTM standards (1.9 to 6.0mm²/s); high viscosity of oil reported showed poor fuel atomization in internal combustion engine, indicating that, biodiesel sample produced can operate efficiently in diesel engine. The refraction index of *J. curcas* oils was within the range EN standards.

3.1. Fatty acid profile of *Jatropha curcas* Methyl ester seed oil

unsaturated fatty acid. Almonic acid was observed with R.A of (17%). These showed that *Jatropha curcas* have higher oxidation stability with less additive to enhanced oxidation stability as shown in Table 2. The Produced biodiesel chart is presented Fig 3.

Figure 1: Jatropha curcas Seeds

Figure 2: Extraction of biofuel in crude stage

Table 1: Physicochemical of properties of J. curcas seed oil

Properties	J. curcas seed oil
Colour	Brown
Moisture (%)	8.0
Yield (%)	75.9
Crude Fiber	6.00
Ash content (°C)	6.04
Carbohydrate Content	19.35
FreeFatty Acids (MgKOH/g)	20.08
Specific Gravity	0.87
Peroxide Value (Mg/I ₂)	0.30
Iodine Value (Mg/I ₂)	110
Viscosity(mm ² /S ⁻¹)	3.8
Flash point (°C)	262
Density Kg/m ³	0.89

Table 2: Fatty acid profile of Jatropha curcas methyl ester seed oil.

N/S	Common name	Systematic name	R.A (%)
1	Palmitic acid	Hexadecanoic acid	7
2	Stearic acid	Octadecanoic acid	26
3	Oleic acid	Cis-9-octadecanoic acid	21
4	Almonic acid	4-oxo-octadeca-9- trans-13-cis-15-tetraenoic acid	17

Table 3: Regeneration of catalyst

Regeneration of catalyst	The catalyst remains after each run	Yield of Nano (vol %) acid- activated)	Yield of Nano (vol%) (calcined)
1	1.8	89.25	92.24
2	1.2	76.50	80.50
3	0.8	83.80	85.70
4	0.6	80.80	82.12
5	0.3	76.50	81.10

3.2 Catalyst reusability

The stability of the nano-catalyst was investigated by reusing it. Sample was calcined after each process. The calcined form was prepared by subjecting the $\text{CoMgFe}_2\text{O}_4$ to 800°C for 2h. The reusability of catalyst for feature transesterification was studied under the transesterification operating conditions for further utilization: methanol: oil (10:2), catalyst (0.75g) and 1hr reaction time. The initial regeneration run yielded 89.25% and 92.24% for the acid-activated and

calcined nano-catalyst to biodiesel. The regeneration dropped to 76.50% and 80.50% respectively, at fifth regeneration run. This similar to (Satya Lakshmi et al., 2020) the reusability of catalyst was further studied by observing some process parameters, variation showed with increase acid-activated at the fourth regeneration and decrease in the catalyst activity due to impurity. Most samples were in accordance with ASTM standards for diesel. [Table 3](#), showed the regeneration of nano-catalyst. The regeneration of

Table 4: Fuel properties of Jatropha curcas seed oil and its derivative

Sample	Density (Kg/m ³)	Flash point(°C)	Calorific value(J/kg)	Pour point(°C)	Viscosity at 70°C(mm ² /s)	Viscosity at 100°C(mm ² /s)	Acid value (mgKOH/g)
Diesel	0.89	78	45,179	-8	2.03	1.43	0.45
J. curcas	0.943	262	43,627	8	13.04	6.07	1.26
J20	0.843	122	45,520	-4	4.30	0.82	0.43
J40	0.855	136	44,355	-2	6.03	1.63	0.70
J60	0.880	152	44,938	2	8.30	1.87	0.86
J80	0.877	176	44,753	4	10.09	2.34	0.89
J100	0.897	189	45,530	6	12.20	3.82	1.12
ASTM D6751	0.8 - 0.9	100	NA	16	NA	NA	0.8

catalyst further, shows that, the leaching of calcium oxide content in the catalyst was the main reasons for the sudden drop in conversion. See fig.4 (Kostic et al., 2016).

3.3 Bio-diesel and its Derivatives

The results of the biodiesel showed derivative properties that, confirm the trans esterification of J. curcas oil using Nano-catalyst shows improves fuel properties significantly. The blending of methyl esters with with petroleum improved significantly its viscosity. Methyl esters/ diesel (20 :70) of the J. curcas feedstock has viscosity that attribute to it recommendation for

powering mobile equipment (Jaichandar and Annamalai, 2011); the higher blends fell within 4D grade of diesel (5.0 -34.4 mm²/s) this could be utilized for stationary equipment (Kostic et.al., 2016; Satya Lakshmi et al., 2020 Okonkwo et al., 2021). The reduction in its viscosity is about the replacing heavy alcohol in the oils sample (glycerol), furthermore, higher viscosity is significant setback in utilization of vegetable bio-oil as an alternative in diesel engines, the trans esterification of animal fats, agricultural residue and vegetable oils for fuel purposes is to reduce their viscosity compared to hydrocarbon. The flash point of the J.

curcas decreased as they were converted to methyl ester from 262 to 110°C. the flash point is the temperature where fuel will commence its vaporization to form an ignitable mixture when it comes in contact with air. The flashpoint showed the safety indicator for fuel. ASTM stated minimum of 130°C flash point of the biodiesel; the process of transesterification, the 2volatile components of the parent oils were reduced (Giakoumis and Sarakatsanis, 2019). ASTM D6751 limit, the fuel properties of the methyl ester/ diesel blends (Ogbu and Ajiwe,2016).

4. Conclusion

Quest of production of alternative source of fuels is intriguing. The use of oil producing seeds in biodiesel production reduces the cost of diesel and reduces the emission of toxic element to the environment. The utilization of *Jatropha curcas* is advantageous because is inexpensive and widely available. We showed vast potential of *J. curcas* for future commercialisation of biodiesel production using nano-catalyst. from our study, the oil yield of *Jatropha curcas* was suitable for commercial biodiesel production, this study shows (54.80%). The activities of nano - catalyst were stable for various blends of biodiesel. The reusability of the catalyst for continuous reaction runs was studied under same operation conditions, the outcome shows that, biofuel yield was high after five runs. Physicochemical properties of the oils aligned with ASTM and EN Standards for biofuel. The percentage of yield shows range of commercialization of biofuel from *J. curcas* to avert the

frailty of fossil-based fuels and their negative environmental outcome when utilized in diesel engines.

Reference

- [1] Akintayo, E. T. & Bayer, E. 2002. *Bioresources Technology*. 85(23), 95 – 97.
- [2] Benghe, M. 2008..*Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research* 44(9), 111-1.
- [3] Berthiaume, D., Tremblay, A., 2006. Oleotek Inc.,NRCan project CO414 CETC-327.
- [4] Calais, P., and Clark, A., 2004 Murdoch University and Western Australian Renewable Fuels Association: Murdoch University, Western Australia.
- [5] Chinmoy, B., Ernest, K., Yanfuy, M. and Bergougou, A. 2009 *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, ISSN 1542 6580, 07(1), 122-126
- [6] Dash, S., Lingfa, P., 2018. IOP Conference Series: material Science and Engineering.IOP Publishing.
- [7] Feitosa, E.A. Xavier, H.S., Randau, K.P., 2012.*Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia* 22, 1181- 1186
- [8] Gholami, A., Pourfayaz, F., Maleki, A., 2020. *Front. Energy Res.* 144.
- [9] Giakoumis, E.G., Sarakatsanis, C.K., 2019. *Energies* 12, 444
- [10] Gubitz, G.M., Mittelbach, M.,& Trabi, M. 1999. *Bioresource Technology Research*, 67(3), 73–82.
- [11] Jaichandar, S., Annamalaai, K., 2011. *Journal of Sustainable Energy & Environment* 2, 71-75.
- [12] Kara, K., Ouanji, F., El Mahi, M., Kacimi, M., Mahfoud, Z., 2019. *Biofuels* 12, 1083 -1089. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17597269.2019.1580972>.
- [13] Kazi, M., Mohammad, M., Roknuzzaman, M. and Asadullah,

- A.G, 2019, International Journal of Mechanical & Mechatronics IJMME-IJENS, 10(2), 3-9
- [14] Kostic, M. D., Velickovic, A.V., Jokovic, N. M., Stamenkovic, O.S., Veljkovic, V.B., 2016. Water Manag. 48, 619-629.
- [15] Kumar, V., Babu, J., Pramod, W., Ramteke, A. M. and Firdaus, J. 2011, International Journal of energy and environment, 34(2), 233-235.
- [16] Laskar, I.B., Rajkumari, K., Gupta, R., Chatterjee, S., Paul, B., Rokhum, L., 2018. RSC Adv. *, 20131 -20142.
- [17] Marchetti, J.M., Miguel, V.U. And E rrazu, A.F. 2017 Renewable Sustainable Energy Reviews, 11(4), 1300-1311.
- [18] Nayak, B.S. & Patel, K.N. 2010 Sains Malaysia 39(2) 951-955.
- [19] Ogbu, I., Ajiwe, V., 2016. Renew, Energy 96, 203-208.
- [20] Ogbu, I.M.. Ajiwe, V.I.E., Okoli, C. P., 2018. BioEnergy Res. 11, 772 - 783.
- [21] Okonkwo, C.P., Ajiwe, V.I., Obiadi, M.C., Okwu, M., 2021, Am. J. Appl. Chem. 9, 154 -163.
- [22] Pikula, K., Zakharenko, A., Stratidakis, A., Razgonova, M., Nosyrev, A., Mezhev, Y., Tsatsakis, A., Golokhvast, K., 2020. Green Chem.Lett. Rev. 13, 275 -294.
- [23] Ramirez, M.V., 2021 Rev. Colombiana Ciencias Pecuarias 34, 155-160.
- [24] Satya Lakshmi, S. B.V., Niju. S., Khadhar Mohamed, M.S.B., Narayanan, A., 2020. Energy sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilisation, and Environmental Effect, pp. 1- 16.
- [25] Singh, D., Sharma, D., Soni, S., Sharma, S., Sharma, P. K., Jhalani, A., 2020. Fuel 262, 116553.
- [26] Thiruvengadaravi, K., Nandagopal, J., Bala, V.S.S., Kirupha, S.D., Vijayalakshmi. P., Sivanesan, S., 2009
- [27] Verma, D., Raj, J., Pal, A., Jain, M., 2016. J. Sci. Innovat. Res. 5,51-58.
- [28] White, P. A., Araujo, J.M., Cercato, L. M., Souza, L. A., Barbosa, A.P.O., Quintans-Junior, L. J., Machado, U. F., Camargo, E.A., Brito, L.C. Santos, M.R.V., 2016. J. Med. Food19. !55-160.

Article History:

Submitted: 2024-08-06

Accepted: 2024-08-10

Published: 2024-08-15